

ENHANCING THE MOIST-HEAT AGING RESISTANCE OF SULFATED CELLULOSE NANOFIBRIL FILMS

Almeida R.O.¹, Ramos A.², Maloney T.³, Belgacem N.⁴, Gamelas J.A.F.¹

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering, CERES, University of Coimbra, Rua Sílvio Lima, Pólo II, 3030-790 Coimbra, Portugal;

² Department of Chemistry, FibEnTech, University of Beira Interior, Rua Marquês d'Ávila e Bolama, 6201-001 Covilhã, Portugal

³ Department of Bioproducts and Biosystems, Aalto University, P.O. Box 16300 Aalto, Finland

⁴ Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LGP2, F-38000 Grenoble, France

jafgas@eq.uc.pt

Cellulose nanofibril (CNF) films are known for their high mechanical strength and optical transparency, good oxygen barrier and reasonable water vapor barrier (at low relative humidity conditions)¹, which has enabled their use in a wide range of applications, including restoration of old paper documents, packaging, electronic devices, etc². Nevertheless, similar to other cellulosic materials, CNF films are susceptible to degradation during natural aging, which can adversely affect their properties and thereby limit their long-term applicability. Despite the significance of this aspect, aging behavior of CNF films is often overlooked in the literature. Therefore, in this work, CNF films prepared from a highly sulfated CNF (2.2 mmol/g) were subjected to accelerated aging tests at 80 °C, 65% of relative humidity (RH) for up to eight days. The sulfated CNF was produced from *Eucalyptus Globulus* kraft pulp fibers through sulfation with a deep eutectic solvent composed of sulfamic acid and urea, followed by high-pressure homogenization. For film preparation, the resulting sulfated CNF suspension was diluted to 0.2 wt%, stirred with a high-shear disperser, cast into polystyrene Petri dishes and left to dry at room temperature for 7 days. The prepared sulfated CNF films (basis weight of ca. 20 g/m²) were then submitted to moist-heat aging, and their degradation behavior was monitored by evaluating the degree of polymerization, pH, crystallinity and thermal stability, as well as their chemical, mechanical and optical properties. Within only two days of aging, a sharp drop in the pH of the films was observed, leading to extensive cellulose depolymerization and severe loss of film mechanical performance. The moist-heat aging process also reduced the thermal stability of the films, induced chemical modifications and caused pronounced yellow/brown discoloration. Overall, these results highlight the extreme sensitivity of sulfated CNF films to moist-heat conditions, mainly driven by acid-catalyzed hydrolysis. To prevent the deterioration of film properties under these conditions, the incorporation of an optimized amount of a reducing agent into the sulfated CNF suspension prior to film formation was investigated. This strategy effectively stabilized the sulfated CNF films, increasing their initial pH and suppressing hydrolytic degradation. After eight days of aging, the treated films retained nearly all of their degree of polymerization and mechanical strength, while their color stability was significantly improved and yellow/brown discoloration effectively prevented. This work demonstrates, for the first time, that although sulfated CNF films degrade rapidly under moist-heat conditions, chemical stabilization provides a simple and effective strategy to preserve their properties.

REFERENCES

1. Nechyporchuk, O.; Belgacem, M. N.; Bras, J. Production of cellulose nanofibrils: a review of recent advances. *Industrial crops and products* **2016**, *93*, 2–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2016.02.016>.
2. Almeida, R.; Ramos, A.; Håkonsen, V.; Maloney, T.; Gamelas, J. Functionalized cellulose nanofiber films as potential substitutes for japanese paper. *Carbohydrate polymer technologies and applications* **2024**, *8*, 100573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carpta.2024.100573>.